

The Technology Adoption of Jajar Legowo System and Direct Seeding System on Rice Farming in the Village of Duria Asi, Wonggeduku District of Konawe Regency, Indonesia.

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Abstract: This study aims to analyze the stage of technology adoption and farmers' behavior toward technology adoption on cropping systems of Jajar Legowo (JLS) and Direct Seeding System (DSS) on rice farming in the village of Duria Asi, Wonggeduku district of Konawe Regency, Indonesia. This research was conducted on March to May 2017. The research approach used is qualitative research. Data collection was conducted through in-depth interviews, participatory observation, documentation, and archival footage. Data were analyzed using qualitative descriptive analysis. The results showed that the application of of jajar legowo planting system has not been widely applied (23%). Farmers' behavior is determined by internal and external factors in determining the technology's adoption ability of Jajar Legowo System and Direct Seeding System. Therefore, cooperation from extension agencies and researchers is needed to increase the ability of farmers' group in rice field farming so that local institution can perform its function better in order to achieve the production target.

Keywords: rice farming, farmers behavior, awareness, interest, evaluation.

I. Introduction

The implementation of cropping system in Konawe Regency, Indonesia is generally done with direct seeding system (DSS). Very few farmers are interested in the recommended planting pattern that is jajar legowo system (JLS). Adoption of technology is essentially a process of acceptance of a new innovations obtained through counseling or through other medias. The admission process by the main actors of paddy rice (farmers) to a new innovation information obtained, can be seen from the acceptance and application of the technology in farming.

The adoption of technological innovation of rice cultivation is influenced by (1) the level of farmers needs to technological innovation, the cosmopolitan nature of farmers, the triability and complexity of technology and the intensity of development, (2) the adoption index of farmers, innovation on rice cultivation technology package varies depending on the type of activity, 3) farmers generally give positive appreciation to researcher-counselor (4) communication factor (Efendy J and Hutapea Y, 2010). Another research pointed out that farmers' adoption index shows the majority on the application of relatively high nursering practices (Ndagi A. H et al, 2016). Apart from the technology characteristics, there are other significant aspects that influence farmer' adoption decisions such as counseling, capital resources, social influences, and institutional factor. (Jamal K et al, 2014).

The phenomenon of paddy farmer behavior is generally done individually with different experience and knowledge, application of technology of paddy field farming is not based on recommended farming system yet, that is jajar legowo system because farmers are still applying direct seeding system, processing is not simultaneous, fertilization does not fit plant's need, pest / disease control in rice crops is inappropriate due to limited knowledge, skills and attitudes of farmers in solving the problem. Farmers who are able to adopt technology can increase rice production and income rather than non-adopters (Wang H et al, 2010). Research on rice cultivation technology adoption was also carried out by Abdulul et al (2018) and Sjakir M et al (2015). A similar study was conducted by Chuchird R et al (2017) on the Influencing Factors of the Adoption of Agricultural Irrigation Technologies and the Economic Returns.

Knowledge and attitudes will not respond directly to a change, recognizing that knowledge and attitude are influenced by the experience, length of farming experience and environment of farmers who are monopolized in the activities of wetland rice farming that hereditary (Rambe M, SS and Honorita B, 2011). Decisions to adopt were mainly influenced by variables related to extensions - training, membership in farmer's group and non-farm employment (Suvedi M et al, 2017). Despite the great potential of agricultural innovations intrinsic factors such as knowledge, perceptions and attitudes of adopter candidates to innovation play a key role, but this is poorly studied (Meijer SS et al, 2015).

II. Research Methods

Type and Research Approach

This type of research is descriptive. The approach used is qualitative research which is a method to explore and understand clearly by describing some social phenomenon of paddy field farming in Duria Asi Village, Wonggeduku Subdistrict of Konawe Regency which is directly related to research concept of technology adoption and farmer behavior on jajar legowo and direct seeding system on rice farming.

Location and Time of Study

The research was conducted on March to May 2017, in Duria Asi Village, Wonggeduku Sub-District, Konawe Regency. This location is one of the centers of high rice production in Konawe Regency. Duria Asi village has 7 farmer groups, 1 combine groups and 1 field officer. All activities of farmer groups are engaged in wetland rice farming.

Data sources

Sources of data in this study were collected from interviews with several informants. The selected informants were from the sub-district apparatus and village officials, community leaders, and members of the farmer group and the combined groups. The data collected is data that can support the needs of data in research until it reaches the level of saturation / adequacy.

Data used in this research are primary data and secondary data. Primary data was obtained through in-depth interviews using questionnaires. Secondary data is obtained from the results of literature review, documentation studies, and norms in the study sites.

III. Results and Discussion

Jajar Legowo System (JLS)

The technology adoption of jajar legowo system is viewed based on the awareness, interest, evaluation, and trial or application. The recommended technology of paddy field farming in the research area is the technology of JLS. The Jajar legowo system is the system of rice planting which has a space interval between two or more (usually two or four) crop lines and one empty row. Legowo term is derived from Javanese language "lego" which means wide and "dowo" which means long. Legowo is also interpreted as a way of planting rice that has several rows and interspersed with an empty row. Introduction of JLS presented by agriculture extension that is planting distance on PLS 2: 1 and type 4: 1 type. In type 2: 1 is 20 cm (between the lines) x 10 cm (margin lines) x 40 cm (empty row) Plant Population in PLS type 2: 1 ie 333.333 clumps, or 1 ha = 10,000 / 1,2m² x 40 clumps = 333,333 clumps. PLS type 4: 1 is a cropping method that has 4 rows and then interrupted by 1 blank line where each end of the line has a distance of ≥ 2 times the distance in the middle row.

Thus, the spacing of Legowo system type 4: 1 is 20 cm (between rows and the middle row) × 10 cm (edge lines) × 40 cm (blank lines). Planting orientation in Legowo 4: 1 full (20 cm - 40 cm) × 10 cm. Population of plants in 1m × 1m = 4 clumps × 10 clumps or 1m² = 40 clumps, or 1 ha = 10,000 / 1m² × 40 clumps = 400,000 clumps. Modification of planting distance of Jajar Legowo system can be done with various considerations. In general, the spacing used is 20 cm and can be modified to 22.5 cm or 25 cm considering rice varieties that will be planted or the level of soil fertility. Jajar Legowo planting system can increase the rice production to 10 tons / ha.

Paddy rice production in Konawe Regency based on the last three years statistic data, showed that in 2014 paddy rice production was 247,979 tons / year, in 2015 production was 252,979 tons / year and 2016 amounted to 6.0 tons / ha (BPS of Konawe Regency, 2017). These data indicate that rice production could be improved by changing the existing pattern of cropping systems, from direct seeding system to jajar legowo system so that paddy rice production annually can be increased. This is in accordance with the results of research by Saridewi and Siregar (2010); (Altalb, A, AT et al, 2015), that the role of counseling and adoption of technologies by farmers are working in synergy to increase rice production.

Direct Seeding System (DSS)

Rice cultivation in DSS requires about a half time more seeds than JLS. Seed needs reaches 30-40 kg / ha. Therefore, the seed to be planted must be of good quality. Before the seed sowing, the seed should be soaked for ± 12 hours and aired for ± 12 hours then the seed can be spread in the terraced rice fields by using direct seeding tool at spacing 20 × 30 × 20 cm. Application of DSS has advantages and disadvantages. The advantages are seen in terms of shorter production period, 7-10 days shorter than JLS, saving manpower, conserve water, increase the yield per unit area, the number of non-productive tillers, while the lack of application of DSS system, the risk of lodging of plants is high, the level of plant damage by rat is quite high, the need for relatively large seed and tillage should be perfect.

Stage of Awareness

Through the role of extensionists in facilitating participatory and dialogical learning processes, farmer groups (FG) does its role in exploring and formulating learning needs, cooperating with other sources of information, as well as the role of combined farmer groups (CFG) as a production unit, can change the level of awareness among farmers members toward JLS and DSS planting system, from 30 people or 100 percent of informants who stated knowing the advantages and disadvantages of JLS system and are aware of the importance of the JLS system as many as 25 people with a percentage 83 percent and who are not aware of the importance of JLS planting system as many as 5 people with a percentage of 17 percent. While aware of the advantages and disadvantages of DSS planting system is 30 people with 100 percent percentage.

Problems in JLS require high work wage while in DSS wage system is very low and easy to be applied so that FG members in Duria Asi Village are more dominantly applying DSS system than JLS

system. Komara (34 Years old) said that: "I apply DSS rice planting system, because of cost factor, low labor wage, easy to apply, less labor, fast production period. It's just that I cannot deny that this way is very risky, because of the high level of lodging of plants, seeds are being used more, and the existence of the problem of plant damage due to attacks of pests are high enough primarily by rats".

Stage of Interest

Through the role of extension or counseling, FG and CFG in the research area, it shows that through mentoring and facilitation of FG members in the preparation of farming plans, learning about JLS and DSS, then from 30 people or 100 percent of informants, who stated interested to implement JLS planting system as many as 17 people with a percentage 57 percent and who have not been interested in implementing JLS planting system as many as 13 people with a percentage 43 percent. While on the DSS planting system, 30 people were interested or 100 percent in percentage.

Stage of Evaluation

The planting system technology offered by the extension to FG members is JLS system. The method used for information technology planting system JLS can be received by members of FG is to implement a demonstration of how the farming acreage of rice farming in the village of Duria Asi. Through this method FG members can see and directly assess the benefits of JLS planting system, how to plant JLS, whether it can be applied easily or not, how the cost of planting and others. The situation in the field showed that through the method of demonstration method, FG members who positively assessed on JLS planting system were 30 people with percentage of 100%, while in DSS planting system there are 10 people who assessed it positively with a percentage of 33.33%. As the following informant told us: "With the example given by the agriculture extension to us through demonstration, I so understand and can asses both the JLS planting system practically, in addition to extend the number of plants, the spacing rows facilitate us to do the cleaning process, fertilizing and pest control" .

Based on these circumstances, it takes the role of agricultural extension, farmer group associations and joint management of farmers to farther enhance their role as farmers' institutions in the village to facilitate the members of the farmer group by working together from various elements ie research institutions, relevant agencies and agricultural extension workers to improve farmer's knowledge and skills so they can increase their capacity themselves to become self-reliant and competitive farmers.

Stage of Adoption

Through the role of local institutions that exist in the village of Duria Asi namely agricultural extension, FG and CFG in carrying out its role in the village then the stage of adopting or receiving technology of JLS there are as many as 7 people with 23% percentage and who do not accept / apply the technology of JLS planting system are 23 people with percentage 77%, whereas in DSS planting system as many as 30 people (100%) informants stated that they accept and apply DSS planting system on heir farming land. This is in accordance with what was said by the informant that: "For the system of jajar legowo, there are only a few members of farmer groups who want to apply the planting system to the rice field although we already understand the benefits, generally members of farmer groups are always looking for a system which is easy, easy to do and does not cost much/expensive".

Based on the informant's report in the research area that in the phase of technology adoption seen on the stage of awareness, interest, assessment, try and adoption phase, related to rice farming indicate that the process of receiving a new innovation in rice farming has not been fully able to do, the public agricultural extension service programmes were regarded as a significant determinant in the adoption of technology. The farmers who received agricultural extension service were more likely to adopt a technology (Walisinghe B, R et al, 2017).

In an effort to build a qualified and reliable agricultural human resources, professional, creative, innovative agricultural extension in the provision of productive counseling, effective and efficient agricultural extension is directed to carry out advisory and consultation tasks for the main actors and

entrepreneurs in developing agribusiness , so the adoption of appropriate technology can run well and in turn enhances the empowerment of the main actors, production, productivity, income and welfare of farmers and their families. Technology adoption of JLS and DSS can be seen in table 1.

Technology	Indicators	Number of Farmers	Percentage
JLS	Awareness Knowing the advantages and disadvantages	25	83
	Interest Interested to apply	17	57
	Evaluation Assessment toward demonstration of ways	30	100
	Trial	7	23
	Adoption	7	23
	DSS	Awareness Knowing the advantages and disadvantages	30
	Interest Interested to apply	30	100
	Evaluation Assessment toward demonstration of ways	10	33
	Trial	23	77
	Adoption	23	77

Table 1 . Technology Adoption of JLS and DSS

Based on the adoption stage and from the Agricultural Extension Statement in the research area, it indicates continuous facilitation of FG members with score of 75 which means extension to FG members in Duria Asi Village is sufficient.

IV. Conclusions and recommendations

The process of receiving a new innovations in rice field farming has not been fully done by the main actors of paddy rice farmers in the village of Duria Asi. This is seen from the application of planting system used where DSS is more dominant applied than JLS.

There is a need for cooperation between research institutes, relevant agencies and agricultural extension workers in order to improve the knowledge, skills and attitudes of farmers so that they are able to adopt JLS planting system technology on rice farming.

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